

OPPORTUNITIES OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE TRAINING OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7818555>

Abstract. *This article highlights the possibilities of information technology in improving the training of future technology teachers.*

Keywords: *technology, electronic textbook, multimedia, electronic didactic tool.*

It is important to study the experiences of foreign countries in implementing educational reforms and use them in practice in implementing the tasks of the National Personnel Training Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Of course, we are more interested in countries that are developing socially and economically and are interested in cooperation with Uzbekistan. One such country is Australia.

In Australia, much attention is paid to the development of the education system at the state level. Especially good conditions are created for students from foreign countries. In Australia, pre-school education and general secondary education (up to the age of 15) are compulsory. After compulsory education, students can choose one of the following types of continuing education.

- technical and further education (TAFE);
- informal labor market and training programs for the population;
- universities (student, master's, doctorate).

Vocational education is considered the most important in Australia at the moment, and it is very widespread in the country. Vocational education in Australia is inextricably linked with industry. Its main purpose is to teach new employees who are students or apprentices to be able to perform their work skillfully. We were more interested in training specialists in the field of information and communication technologies in Australia.

Educational services in accordance with world education standards are offered in the universities, and at the same time fundamental pedagogical researches are conducted in connection with it.

Vocational education institutions provide practical education focused on specific branches of production. Almost all curricula and programs of educational institutions of this type cover the content of production practice or business internship. In this case, the pupil or student will have practical skills in the specialty of his choice. This situation is inextricably linked with further changes in the economy of developing countries, increased competition in the global product market, the formation of the information society, and fundamental qualitative changes in the international market of goods. Electronic learning (e-learning) or distance learning is widely introduced in educational institutions. Training is organized on the basis of CD-ROMs, the

Internet, individual consultations on teleconferences, printed educational materials, etc. 3 methods are mainly used in online education:

- the Internet is used to improve traditional (day and evening) or part-time education (adjunct mode);

- The Internet is used as part of the educational process in the classroom or correspondence education (mixed mode);

- the Internet is used as the main means of teaching during the study of the entire course or a certain program (fotalli online mode). In the Australian education system, the concepts of "teaching technology", "e-learning" are often mentioned. This shows that special importance is attached to the use of information technologies in education. Currently, various technologies used in the field of education provide a technologically rich learning environment for pupils and students. In this, they can analyze ideas, conduct research and present the results of their work to others.

Educational technologies allow learners not only to get acquainted with information (on disk or on the Internet), but also to actively communicate with other people at local, national and international levels through e-mail or video chats. The following are important in the activities of educators and learners:

- Software for processing texts, expressing ideas and concepts, as well as preparing reports and presentations:

Diagrams, tables, graphic packages and visual tools that are useful in the presentation of visual materials and in accounting work, as well as in conducting independent research on Internet pages;

- exercises, modeling;

- multimedia, illustration

- CD-ROMs for obtaining information via the Internet, databases for data collection and analysis, data in electronic spreadsheets in EXSEL format. The use of information technology in education has changed the perception of the curriculum. Students had the opportunity to get a wide range of information. They can connect to global learning networks, participate in data collection worldwide, or read diaries and travel in virtual worlds. In many educational activities conducted using information technologies, students gain more knowledge than in regular classrooms with limited access to information technologies. In the organization of education based on information and communication technologies in Australia, special attention is paid to the following:

- launch full open education for the domestic and foreign markets

- providing the educational process with modern information technologies (material and technical base):

Creating all necessary conditions for working and exchanging information through the Internet. In the educational process, the main object (person) is not the teacher, but the learner. Attention is always paid to his perfection. They use the internet effectively.

After analyzing the activities of several educational institutions in the field of information and communication technologies in Australia, we were convinced of the following:

- curricula and programs in educational institutions are in accordance with international educational standards;

- the teaching methodology is regularly revised;

- enough textbooks and teaching-methodical literature;

- educational institutions are highly equipped with technology, especially computer technology and telecommunications,

-highly qualified employees are involved in educational institutions, and they are good from the material point of view, all of them serve to increase the effectiveness of education.

In Australia, non-required subjects are not necessarily taught to learners, but rather they are helped to find the necessary material related to their professional activities. Procedures for selecting subjects and programs suitable for the specializations chosen by the students have been developed. During the theoretical training, students hardly write down the content of the lecture. They will be given handouts in advance. In addition, they use the electronic version of the lecture, and many educational materials are presented with the help of multimedia. Times are different now. Society is rapidly changing, and market relations are settling. In such conditions, education cannot exist in accordance with the laws of the market. It is necessary to expand the financial and economic independence of all educational subjects, to finance them.

It is desirable to establish new specializations in e-commerce, communication and multimedia, e-business, technology and information technologies in the field of business in educational institutions of our republic.

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